

Unraveling the Dynamics of Social Media Engagement and Activism among Far Eastern University Students: A Demographic and Attitudinal Analysis

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ABSTRACT: As multiple generations continue to engage in social media and activists, the researchers saw this as an opportunity to influence change. This study explored how technology, particularly social media platforms, helps shape activism among Far Eastern University students, containing 80 participants from various academic years. Through analysis of the engagement, the study intended to understand which social media platforms are the most and least effective for promoting social change. The researchers used a quantitative approach with survey questionnaires, exploring the students' views about social media activism. Integrating data analysis that includes descriptive and inferential statistics provides valuable insights for activists, policymakers, and educators navigating the dynamic realm of social media activism. Eventually, the data shows Instagram is the most popular site for social media activity at Far Eastern University, with Threads receiving the least attention. Students mostly utilize social media for communication, information searching, and self-expression, motivated by socio-political interests and a desire to belong. The study emphasizes the strong link between social media use and online activist activity, implying a transformative effect. Future studies should broaden demographics and use mixed-methods approaches, focusing on capacity-building activities for student activists focused on social media advocacy to achieve positive societal change.

KEYWORDS: Digital Addiction, Digital Age, Online Engagement, Social Movements, Trends

INTRODUCTION

In a generation where digital connectivity touches every area of human life, activism has learned new ways to express itself, influence others, and mobilize resources. This research explored the relationship between activism and technology, exploring how digital platforms function as vital resources for promoting significant change on a global scale and how they empower the students of Far Eastern University, amplify voices, and foster global solidarity. This study began because digital technology has revolutionized traditional ways to engage in activism. It is undeniable that the emergence of social media and the internet over the last few decades has had a profound impact on how people interact in politics and society (Owen, 2019). It has given rise to a new era of activism that leverages the power of online platforms.

Activism is the collaborative effort of individuals or groups to promote social, political, or cultural change. It entails acting to address specific situations, question norms, and advance justice. To influence public opinion and policy, activists use a variety of tactics, including protests, campaigns, and awareness-raising (Brooks, 2023). Innovations like technology emerge throughout time. Technology has transformed how we live, work, and communicate with one another. Technology has made human life very easy and accessible through communication with humans, resourcing, access to medical care, job applications, etc. However, it also has some negative impacts, such as cyberbullying and digital addiction (KeyTech, 2023). Digital activism provides new ways to engage with protesters and has proven to be a powerful instrument for organizing local politics (Fuentes, 2014). How activism and technology interact, particularly social media, is changing how Far Eastern University students engage with societal issues. In this technologically connected world, when everything is interconnected, this connection transcends national boundaries and fosters unity and empowerment.

Social Media activism has become an important topic of discussion in today's digital age, with such online platforms as effective tools for promoting social change and inspiring groups of people to act together (Chon & Park, 2019). Practitioners and

academics need to understand the dynamics and effects of online platforms on activism as technology continues to alter political involvement. This study explores the significance of investigating the use of digital technologies in social media activism, providing insight into how these tools affect social change, advocacy campaigns, and public policy. This study's results directly impact stakeholders, including social media corporations, legislators, and activists, since they can provide valuable insights to successfully build on their tactics, platforms, and regulations to cross the dynamic landscape of online activism. This study may also apply to educators and students, providing insight into how social movements evolve because of digital technologies and what it means for the next generation of activists using online platforms.

According to the study made by Chon and Park (2019) where they take a new approach to analyzing activism by integrating the Situational Theory of Problem Solving (STOPS), opinions regarding media hostility, the impact of injustice, and social media effectiveness in both online and offline settings. This theoretical framework seeks to close the gap in previous research that frequently differentiates social media activism from offline activism. Given that past studies, such as the Situational Theory of Publics (1984) and the Exploration of Connective Action (2012), have helped lay the foundation for understanding the public's involvement and online engagements. These studies have not fully captured which social media platform produces the highest and lowest engagement and the factors behind it. Doing so can provide a better understanding of how social media can be used for activism beyond traditional approaches to collaborative action.

The study's relevance to only three controversial subjects and its dependence on a specific sample from Amazon's Mechanical Turk limit the applicability of its conclusions despite its different approach (Chon & Park, 2019). These limitations highlight the need for additional research that covers a wider range of topics and uses more representative sample strategies. However, the study's integrated approach, which emphasizes the collectively effective interaction between social media platforms and in-person activism, significantly contributes to the area. It establishes a standard for future studies investigating the complex relationship between activism and the digital era. It promotes a more comprehensive analysis of how online involvement, such as social media, influences offline action and vice versa.

While social media has been primarily used for leisure, it can also be a tool that drives change. Social media also lowered the barriers to citizens' participation and gradually increased collective action (Malinen et al., 2020). Social media platforms play an essential role in social intercourse and participation in citizens' political activities as they have a notable impact (Koiranen et al., 2019). According to the research made by Dookhoo (2019), increasing engagement in a certain social media platform can help activists utilize these platforms and gather further increases in support, making the efforts of activism more important. Moreover, exploring which platforms influence social media activism can help identify which platforms are conducive to activism. Examining social media activism among Far Eastern University students emphasizes the essential topics that need further investigation. The study intends to determine which social media platform produces the highest and lowest engagement. It also explores the factors influencing these engagements and establishes opportunities for activists to leverage these platforms. Also, the study seeks to provide recommendations for social platforms with less engagement and utilizing surveys for data collection. By examining these aspects, the study hopes to provide information to the growing body of literary works about social media activism while also focusing on the capability of social media platforms as tools for change.

Research Objectives

1. To determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Age;
 - b. Gender;
 - c. Race/Ethnicity;
 - d. Year in College.
2. To explore the prevalent social media platforms Far Eastern University students use.
3. To assess the perceived impact of various social media engagement factors.
4. To examine respondents' perspectives regarding online and offline activism.
5. To evaluate attitudes toward socio-political issues among Far Eastern University students.
6. To investigate the motivational factors that drive student activism on social media platforms at Far Eastern University.

METHODOLOGY

The study applied a quantitative approach, utilizing the standard survey questionnaires from Dookhoo (2015) to gather numerical data and conduct statistical analysis to address research questions with factual evidence. A stratified random sampling method was employed to ensure representation from each academic year (Hayes, 2024). The survey questionnaires included quantitative data on FEU students' engagement in social media activism, their preferred social media platform, and their insights regarding social media activism, aiding in determining the platforms with the highest and lowest engagement levels. This quantitative approach aimed to ensure efficiency in data gathering and oversee a systematic review of various patterns related to social media activism among FEU students. Online survey questionnaires were utilized, and the data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics describe the data set by showing the relationship between elements in a population sample using mean and standard deviation (Hayes, 2024). Multiple regression was justified under inferential statistics due to numerous dependent variables and one independent variable. This methodology analyzed the process of gathering quantitative data to assess students' viewpoints on digital activism and responding to research questions with fact-based support (Bhat, 2023). Efforts were made to ensure various participation across academic years, reduce sampling biases, and guarantee reliable, accurate data while adhering to guidelines for obtaining participants' consent and protecting their personal information.

The survey participants were among the 1st to 4th year students of Far Eastern University (FEU) to guarantee adequate sample size. The study aims to gather 20 students per year level, totaling 80 participants overall. The researchers approached potential participants in various campus spots and through posting on 'One Piyu Community' a Facebook page that has various members of legit students at Far Eastern University or through Facebook friends that are currently enrolled at FEU, providing information about the study, and inviting them to participate voluntarily. To maintain consistency and reliability in data collection while accommodating variations, a published survey questionnaire was the primary data collection instrument. The survey titled "How Millennials Engage in Social Media Activism: A Uses and Gratification Approach" was the instrument that helped maintain uniformity in data collection, making the results comparable and generalizable. To ensure ethical conduct, informed consent was obtained from all participants, assuring them of the voluntary nature of their involvement. Moreover, strict measures were implemented to maintain confidentiality and anonymity throughout the study. Participants were debriefed after the survey to address concerns and ensure a transparent and respectful research process.

Survey questionnaires were used to gather empirical data and statistically analyze them to determine the different patterns and trends in how students participate in social media activism discussions and their preferences for various social media platforms. This study used descriptive statistics. The researchers identified the three highest values by getting the meaning of each variable. They used sample standard deviation to analyze the variability within the data set and to help measure the FEU students' involvement level and social media platform preferences. Credibility and transparency of the findings were ensured through the data analysis process by carefully documenting all decisions and interpretations made. The researcher used software tools designed for quantitative analysis, such as Microsoft Excel (Brookfield, 2023), to strengthen how data is managed, processed, and visualized to enhance efficiency and accuracy. Using a quantitative analysis approach, the study intends to provide a comprehensive understanding of FEU students' involvement in the discourse of social media activism and give insights into which social media platform offers the highest and lowest engagement.

Research Instruments

The researcher used a survey questionnaire from Dookhoo (2015), a study called "How Millennials Engage in Social Media Activism: A Uses and Gratification Approach." The study thus consists of five variables: demographic questions such as age, gender, race/ethnicity, year in college, and their preferred social media platform, as the independent variable where it utilizes a seven-point Likert type scale which includes a rating scale ranging from one to seven where seven signified always, six for usually, five for frequently, four for sometimes, three for occasionally, two for rarely, and one for never. The other four variables consist of factors affecting engagements, online activism, offline activism, and activism identification, which are the dependent variables. It also utilizes a seven-point Likert-type scale where seven indicates strongly agree, six for agree, five for somewhat agree, four for neither agree or disagree, three for somewhat disagree, two for disagree, and one for strongly disagree. The students from Far Eastern University were asked for their consent regarding their participation in the study before answering the survey to ensure they felt safe and comfortable answering.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section interprets the results from the statistical tests conducted in the study. Through interpreting these results, the researcher aims to provide insights into the different aspects of social media activism among Far Eastern University students. These insights included understanding the demographic profile of the participants in terms of age, gender, race/ethnicity, and their year in college, as well as exploring the prevalent social media platforms students use. Moreover, the researchers seek to assess the perceived impact of the factors influencing social media engagement, examine the students' perspectives on online and offline activism, evaluate the attitudes concerning socio-political issues, and investigate the motivational factors driving student activism on social media platforms. With these interpretations, the researchers aim to provide comprehensive information about the dynamics of social media activism within the university context.

A. Demographic Profile

Table 1. Respondents' Demographic Profile in terms of Age, Gender, Race/Ethnicity, and Current Year Level

Age	Frequency	Percent (%)
18-20 years old	45	56.3
21-23 years old	30	37.5
24-26 years old	5	6.3
Gender		
Male	31	38.8
Female	47	58.8
Prefer not to say	2	2.5
Race/Ethnicity		
Asian	80	100
Year in College		
Freshman	21	26.3
Sophomore	20	25
Junior	20	25
Senior	19	23.8
TOTAL	80	100

Table 1 shows the demographic data of the respondents: 45 (56.3%) respondents are between the ages of 18-20 years; 30 (37.5%) respondents are between 21-23 years; and 5 (6.3%) respondents are between 24-26 years old; 31 (38.8%) respondents are Male, 47 (58.8%) respondents are Female and 2 (2.5%) preferred not to say their gender; 80 (100%) which indicates that all respondent were Asian; 21 (26.3%) of the respondents are from Freshman, 20 (25%) from Sophomore, 20 (25%) from Junior, and 19 (23.8%) from Senior.

Table 2 below shows one of the research objectives: to determine which social media platforms produce the most and least interactions among the students. To address this, the mean scores and standard deviation for the frequency of social media platform responses were reviewed with a 7-point scale.

B. Prevalent Social Media Platforms

Table 2. Social Media Platform with Most and Least Interaction

Items	M	SD	I	Rank
Instagram	6.03	1.27	Always	1
Facebook	5.81	1.56	Usually	2
TikTok	5.81	1.72	Usually	2
YouTube	5.46	1.48	Usually	3
X (Twitter)	4.03	1.97	Frequently	4
Thread	1.67	1.34	Rarely	5
OVERALL MEAN	4.80	1.56	FREQUENTLY	

Legend: 0.01-1.00 (never), 1.01-2.00 (rarely), 2.01-3.00 (occasionally), 3.01-4.00 (Sometimes), 4.01-5.00 (Frequently), 5.01-6.00 (Usually), and 6.01-7.00 (Always).

Table 2 reveals that the most used social media platform among FEU students is Instagram (M=6.03, SD=1.27); this is to be interpreted as “agree.” According to Sharma (2024), more than 500 million people are daily active users of Instagram, and 59% of micro-influencers consider Instagram the platform where they get the most engagement to reach more people as there is less competition. It also reveals that the least-used social media platform among FEU students is Threads (M=1.67, SD=1.34), to be interpreted as “rarely.” As Boshernitsan (2023) said, given that it garnered over 100 million users on its release, there has been an 80% drop in its daily active users. The study’s findings revealed that the overall average is 4.80, interpreted as “frequently” with the student's response about the prevalent social media platforms used by Far Eastern University students. This shows that students today utilize social media as modern technology arises, as it is used for communication and connecting people for social interaction and academic areas (Tayo, 2019).

C. Perceived Impact of Various Factors Influencing Social Media Engagements

Table 3. Perceived Impact of Various Factors Influencing Social Media Engagements among FEU Students

Items	M	SD	I	Rank
<i>3.1 I use social media platforms: Convenience</i>				
1. To communicate with friends, family.	6.74	0.61	Strongly Agree	1
2. Because it is cheaper	6.08	1.28	Strongly Agree	2

3. People don't have to be there the exact time you post a comment or send a message	5.88	1.46	Agree	3
MEAN	6.23	1.12	STRONGLY AGREE	

3.2 Social media platforms allow me: Information Seeking

To get information for free	6.36	0.84	Strongly Agree	2
To look for information.	6.44	0.84	Strongly Agree	1
To see what is out there	6.23	0.91	Strongly Agree	4
To get information easier	6.33	0.94	Strongly Agree	3
To learn what my social connection are posting about	5.53	1.4	Agree	6
To keep up with the current issues and events	6.1	1.24	Strongly Agree	5
MEAN	6.165	1.03	STRONGLY AGREE	

3.3 I utilize social media platforms: Interpersonal Utility/Social Interaction

To help others	5.07	1.23	Agree	7
To meet new people	5.18	1.30	Agree	6
To participate in discussions	5	1.37	Somewhat Agree	8
To show other encouragement	5.27	1.35	Agree	5
To belong to a group with the same interest as mine	5.6	1.31	Agree	3
To express myself freely.	5.75	1.34	Agree	2
To give my input	4.97	1.48	Somewhat Agree	9
To get more points of view	5.87	1.18	Agree	1
To tell others what to do	3.88	1.79	Neither Agree nor Disagree	10
Because I wonder what other people are talking about	5.33	1.55	Agree	4
MEAN	5.19	1.39	AGREE	

3.4 I utilize social media platforms: Pass Time

Because it passes time when I'm bored	6.41	1.02	Strongly Agree	1
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To occupy my time	6.16	1.15	Strongly Agree	2
Because it allows me to unwind	5.97	1.29	Agree	4
Because I have nothing better to do	5.19	1.69	Agree	7
Because it relaxes me	5.39	1.36	Agree	5
Because it's a habit, just something to do	5.99	1.13	Agree	3
Because I can forget about school, work, or other things	5.38	1.57	Agree	6
Because there's no one else to talk to or be with	4.3	1.9	Somewhat Agree	8
MEAN	5.59	1.39	AGREE	

3.5 For me social media is: Entertainment

Entertaining	6.46	0.82	Strongly Agree	1
I just like to use it	6.18	0.9	Strongly Agree	2
Enjoyable	6.09	1.12	Strongly Agree	3
MEAN	6.242	0.95	STRONGLY AGREE	

3.6 With social media: Control

I want someone to do something for me	3.5	1.96	Neither Agree nor Disagree	2
2. I tell other what to do	3.53	1.83	Neither Agree nor Disagree	1
MEAN	3.513	1.9	NEITHER AGREE NOR DISAGREE	

OVERALL MEAN 5.49 1.3 STRONGLY AGREE

Legend: 0.01-1.00 (strongly disagree), 1.01-2.00 (disagree), 2.01-3.00 (somewhat disagree), 3.01-4.00 (neither agree or disagree), 4.01-5.00 (somewhat agree), 5.01-6.00 (agree), and 6.01-7.00 (strongly agree).

Table 3 above includes subtopics that address objective 3, which is to understand how social media platforms can encourage social change. The indicated items are the categories under factors affecting engagement. The researchers ranked from 1 to 3 for each subsection, with the highest mean answering objective 3, which is how FEU students show encouragement by using social media platforms. The table's findings are supported by research conducted by Graham (2023) and organizations such as the National Network to End Domestic Violence (2019b) and Wallace University (2022b).

Table 3.1 reveals that FEU students use social media primarily for its convenience features. The mean score for the "Convenience" dimension is 6.23 (SD = 1.12), indicating that students strongly agree to use social media for its convenience. It shows that FEU students utilized social media platforms to communicate with friends and family (Item = 1, M = 6.74, SD = 0.61), interpreted as strongly agreeing. (National Network to End Domestic Violence, 2019b) indicates that social media platforms allow everyone who uses them to communicate real-time interactions and facilitate the exchange of information. Next, FEU students

utilized social media platforms because it is cheaper (Item 2, $M = 6.08$, $SD = 1.28$), which is interpreted as “strongly agree,” and because people do not have to be there the exact time you post a comment or send a message (Item 3, $M = 5.88$, $SD = 1.46$) which is also interpreted as “agree.” Therefore, through social media platforms and their efficacy and expansive nature of communication, FEU students can easily communicate information with their social networks. They can easily encourage social change using social media platforms as their primary communication tool.

Additionally, with the help of technology and social media platforms, it has become much easier for individuals to gather all the information that is essential to them (Walden University, 2022b). This supports table 3.2, “Social media platforms allow me: Information Seeking,” which is that social media platforms allow FEU students to look for information they need (Item 2, $M = 6.44$, $SD = 0.84$), interpreted as strongly agreeing. Next, social media platforms allow students to get information for free (Item 1, $M = 6.36$, $SD = 0.84$), interpreted as strongly agreeing, and to get information easier (Item 4, $M = 6.33$, $SD = 0.94$), which is also interpreted as strongly agreeing. The mean score for the “Information Seeking” subtopic is 6.16 ($SD = 1.03$), indicating that FEU students agree to use social media to seek information. The increased access to information can lead to greater awareness of social issues among FEU students. Therefore, social media platforms can be seen as instruments for social change since they provide people with the means to support causes, spread awareness, and other objectives.

Table 3.3, titled “I utilize social media platforms: Interpersonal Utility/Social Interaction,” reveals that FEU students used social media platforms to get more points of view (Item 8, $M = 5.87$, $SD = 1.18$) interpreted as “agree,” to express themselves freely (Item 6, $M = 5.75$, $SD = 1.34$), interpreted as “agree,” and to belong to a group with the same interest as mine (Item 5, $M = 5.6$, $SD = 1.31$), which is also to be interpreted as “agree.” The mean score for the “Interpersonal Utility/Social Interaction” subtopic is 5.19 ($SD = 1.39$), meaning that FEU students agree that they use social media platforms for social interaction as Graham (2023) signifies that we can use social media platforms as megaphones to spark meaningful conversations. We can raise awareness about major social issues and draw attention to them through our voices.

Next is table 3.4 titled “I utilize social media platforms: Pass Time,” which reveals that FEU students also utilized social media platforms as a pass time because it passes the time when they are bored (Item 1, $M = 6.41$, $SD = 1.02$), interpreted as strongly agreeing, also to occupy the students time (Item 2, $M = 6.16$, $SD = 1.15$), interpreted as strongly agreeing, and lastly because it had become a habit for them and become just something to do (Item 6, $M = 5.99$, $SD = 1.13$), which is interpreted as agreeing. The mean score for the “Pass Time” subtopic is 5.59 ($SD = 1.39$), indicating that FEU students agree to use social media as a pastime. Therefore, social media platforms serve as both a means of entertainment and a habitual pastime for FEU students when they seek to fill idle time. According to Chu & Cheng (2021), who conducted an online survey on college students in Hong Kong, the use of social media platforms, although helpful for students to share, discuss, and search information, is also easily distracted by social media's entertainment and social functions.

Table 3.5 shows what social media is for students in terms of entertainment. The table reveals that social media for FEU students is primarily used for entertainment. The mean score for the “Entertainment” subtopic is 6.24 ($SD = 0.95$), indicating that FEU students strongly agree that they use social media for entertainment. Specifically, the students strongly agree that social media is entertaining ($M = 6.46$, $SD = 0.82$), they like to use it ($M = 6.18$, $SD = 0.90$), and they find it enjoyable ($M = 6.09$, $SD = 1.12$). This suggests that FEU students heavily rely on social media platforms as a source of entertainment and leisure, using them to pass the time, occupy their minds, and fulfill a habitual need for engagement. The data highlights the significant role social media plays in the daily lives of FEU students, serving as a primary means of entertainment and fulfilling their desire for enjoyment and relaxation.

Lastly, table 3.6, titled “With social media: Control,” reveals that FEU students have a neutral stance when it comes to using social media for control purposes. The mean score for the “Control” dimension is 3.5125 ($SD = 1.9$), indicating that students neither agree nor disagree that they use social media to control others or have others do things for them. Specifically, students neither agree nor disagree that they tell others what to do ($M = 3.53$, $SD = 1.83$) or want someone to do something for them ($M = 3.6$, $SD = 1.96$). This implies that while FEU students heavily use social media for entertainment and leisure, it does not play a significant role in their desire to control or influence others. The data suggests a balanced and neutral approach to using social media for control-related purposes among the FEU student population. The study's findings revealed an overall average of 5.57, interpreted as “agree” with the student’s response about the perceived impact of various factors influencing social media engagement among FEU students.

As a result, social media platforms enable FEU students and individuals to contribute to social change by allowing them to voice their ideas, raise awareness, and engage in conversations.

D. Respondents’ Perspectives on Online and Offline Activism

Table 4. Respondents’ Perspectives in Terms of Online and Offline Activism.

Items	M	SD	I	Rank
<i>4.1 Online Activism</i>				
1. Posted a status/tweeted about a social-political issue	4.3	2	Somewhat Agree	3
2. Liked or favorite a post about a social-political issue.	5	2	Somewhat Agree	1
3. Commented on a post about social media	3.9	1.9	Neither Agree nor Disagree	5
4. Shared or retweeted a post about social-political issues.	5	2	Somewhat Agree	
5. Used an activist hashtag in a social media post/tweet	4	2	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4
6. Signed an Online Petition	4	2	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4
7. Mobilized online support for a social-political issue	4.4	2	Somewhat Agree	2
8. Generated awareness about a social-political issue using social media.	5	2	Somewhat Agree	1
9. Prompted social connection to sign an online petition for social-political issue	4	2	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4
10. Shared information about a protest or boycott surrounding a social-political issue on social media	4	2	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4
11. Shared your experience about participating/supporting a social-political issue on social media	4	2	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4
12. Shared socially- or politically-charged images or photos on social media	4	2	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4
13. Changed your social media profile picture surrounding a social-political issue	3	2	Somewhat Disagree	4
14. Donated money to a social-political issue using social media	3	2	Somewhat Disagree	4
15. Attempted to raise money for a social-political issue using social media	3	2	Somewhat Disagree	4

16. Unfriended or unfollowed someone on social media because of their social-political posts/tweets	4	2	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4
17. Friended or followed a political leader or decision make on social media	4	2	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4
18. Contacted a political leader or decision maker through email or social media	3	2	Somewhat Disagree	4
19. Generally speaking, I prefer not to engage in social-political issues online	4	2	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4
20. I do not like to voice my personal social-political beliefs on social media	4	2	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4
21. I do not use social media to engage in social-political issues	4	2	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4
22. I do not agree with many online views of those in my social network	4	1	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4
MEAN	4	2	SOMEWHAT AGREE	

4.2 Offline Activism

1. Attended an in-person informational session about a social-political issue	2.73	1.78	Somewhat Disagree	15
2. Volunteered with an organization that support social-political issues	2.94	1.84	Somewhat Disagree	13
3. Encouraged others to sign a petition offline	3.10	2	Neither Agree nor Disagree	9
4. Participated in fundraising activities offline to obtain donors	2.90	1.96	Somewhat Disagree	14
5. Donated money to support a cause surrounding a social-political issue	3	1.76	Somewhat Disagree	10
6. Participated in a boycott	3.78	2.2	Neither Agree nor Disagree	2
7. Participated in a rally or march	2.63	1.75	Somewhat Disagree	16
8. Participated in a sit-in or public protest	2.40	1.60	Somewhat Disagree	19
9. Shared information offline about a protest or boycott surrounding a social-political issue	3.63	2.16	Neither Agree nor Disagree	3
10. Shared your experiences with others offline about participating/supporting a social-political issue	3.41	2.08	Neither Agree nor Disagree	6

11. Created poster or fliers surrounding a social-political issue	2.50	1.70	Somewhat Disagree	18
12. Distributed information offline surrounding a social-political issue in-person	3	1.90	Somewhat Disagree	11
13. Participated in a “tabling” (where one sets up a table and engage with the members of the public to provide information) or informational event	2.30	1.50	Somewhat Disagree	21
14. Mobilized offline support for a social-political issue	2.60	1.70	Somewhat Disagree	17
15. Generated offline awareness about a social-political issue	3	1.90	Somewhat Disagree	12
16. Debated a social-political issue with friends or family in-person	4	2.2	Neither Agree nor Disagree	1
17. Wrote a letter and sent in by traditional mail to a political leader or decision maker	2.40	1.50	Somewhat Disagree	20
18. Contacted a political leader or decision maker by telephone/cellphone	2.16	1.31	Somewhat Disagree	22
19. Generally speaking, I prefer not to engage in social-political issues offline	3.21	1.89	Neither Agree nor Disagree	8
20. I do not like to voice my personal social-political beliefs offline	3.36	1.88	Neither Agree nor Disagree	7
21. I do not use offline platforms to engage in social-political issues	3.50	1.90	Neither Agree nor Disagree	5
22. I do not agree with many offline views of those in my close network	3.56	1.64	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4
MEAN	3	1.83	SOMEWHAT DISAGREE	
OVERALL MEAN	3	2	NEITHER AGREE NOR DISAGREE.	

Legend: 0.01-1.00 (strongly disagree), 1.01-2.00 (disagree), 2.01-3.00 (somewhat disagree), 3.01-4.00 (neither agree or disagree), 4.01-5.00 (somewhat agree), 5.01-6.00 (agree), and 6.01-7.00 (strongly agree).

Table 4 reveals the perspectives of FEU students on online and offline activism, focusing on the top three highest items in each subsection. The study conducted by Marcaida (2020) supports these results.

Regarding online activism, which is Table 4.1, the majority of FEU students strongly agreed with liking or favoriting a post about a social-political issue (Item 2, M = 5, SD = 2), sharing or retweeting a post about social-political issues (Item 4, M = 5, SD = 2), and generating awareness about social-political issues using social media (Item 8, M = 5, SD = 2). These results indicate a strong preference for utilizing online platforms for activism. Additionally, students somewhat agreed with mobilizing online support for a social-political issue (Item 7, M = 4.4, SD = 2) and posting a status about the social-political issue (Item 1, M = 4.3,

SD = 2). These results align with the study by Marcaida (2020), which emphasizes that certain students view online platforms, particularly social media, as effective tools for political engagement. They contend that social media democratizes access to information, promotes involvement, and gives people the voice to voice their opinions publicly.

On the other hand, for offline activism which is table 4.2, the top three highest items where FEU students engaged the most include debating a social-political issue with friends or family in-person (Item 16, M = 4, SD = 2.2), participating in a boycott (Item 6, M = 3.78, SD = 2.2), and sharing information offline about a protest or boycott surrounding a social-political issue (Item 9, M = 3.63, SD = 2.16). Despite these activities, the overall trend shows a preference for online activism, with a hesitancy towards direct offline engagement in political activism. Additionally, students somewhat disagreed with not agreeing with many offline views of those in their close network (Item 22, M = 3.56, SD = 1.64) and not using offline platforms to engage in social-political issues (Item 21, M = 3.50, SD = 1.90). Furthermore, the overall mean (M = 3, SD = 2) is interpreted as the respondents “neither agree nor disagree” with engaging in both online and offline activism. The standard deviation of 2 suggests some variability in the respondents’ perceptions, indicating that opinions may vary among the sample variation. The findings suggest that FEU students tend to lean towards online activism compared to offline activism, possibly due to the perceived safety and accessibility of engaging in political issues through social media platforms.

E. Evaluate Attitudes Toward Socio-Political Issues Among Far Eastern University Students

Table 5. Activism Identification

Items	M	SD	I	Rank
1. It is important to me to be involved with social-political issues	5.07	1.67	Agree	1
2. I see myself as a social-political activist.	3.47	1.67	Neither Agree nor Disagree	5
3. My friends see me as a social-political activist.	3.21	1.67	Neither Agree nor Disagree	6
4. When a social-political issue is raised, I follow the issue regularly via any of the following a) on social media b) in person or on television c) television news of a newspaper	4.26	1.87	Somewhat Agree	2
5. It is very important that I am a social-political activist.	3.83	1.75	Neither Agree nor Disagree	3
6. I dislike people who are not social-political activists.	3.52	1.78	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4
7. I display the logo or sign of a social-political issue on social media, at my place of work (or university), where I like, or on my clothing.	3.14	1.74	Neither Agree nor Disagree	7
OVERALL MEAN	3.78	1.73	NEITHER AGREE NOR DISAGREE	

Legend: 0.01-1.00 (strongly disagree), 1.01-2.00 (disagree), 2.01-3.00 (somewhat disagree), 3.01-4.00 (neither agree or disagree), 4.01-5.00 (somewhat agree), 5.01-6.00 (agree), and 6.01-7.00 (strongly agree).

Table 5 reveals answers to objective 5, which is to investigate what variables motivate students at Far Eastern University to engage in activism on social media platforms. The results are supported by the studies conducted by Lindsay (2020) and Ralph (2022).

Item 1 reveals that most FEU students who answered the survey indicated that it is important for them to be involved in or have knowledge of social-political issues ($M = 5.075$, $SD = 1.667$), which is interpreted as agreeing. Lindsay (2020) indicates that politics can change individuals' perspectives, and keeping up with the happenings in the world can establish individuals' interpretations of the issues that arise every day. FEU students are driven to participate in social media activism because they understand the importance of political events and desire to be current on social-political issues.

Additionally, item 2 suggests that when social-political issues are raised, the respondents follow them regularly through various mediums such as social media, in-person discussions, television news, or newspapers ($M = 4.26$, $SD = 1.87$), interpreted as somewhat agreeing. In these days of pandemics, protests, economic downturns, and global angst, a recent report shows consumers increasingly turn to social media and messaging services for news (Vorhaus, 2022). This reveals that the respondents shift towards digital platforms as primary sources of news and information, particularly during times of crisis or heightened social-political activity. This trend underscores the importance of understanding and leveraging digital channels for effective communication and engagement with audiences on critical issues.

The last item in Table 5 reveals that most students at FEU who answered the survey "neither agree nor disagree" need to be social-political activists ($M = 3.83$, $SD = 1.75$). FEU students offer a positive attitude towards social-political issues. Furthermore, the study's finding revealed an overall of ($M = 3.78$, $SD = 1.73$) to be interpreted as "neither agree nor disagree," showing that the attitude of FEU students is neutral in identifying their activism leniency about social-political issues.

As for the null hypothesis, the researchers utilize the multiple regression analysis to examine the relationship between which type of social media platform is used and the level of engagement in online activism. Types of social media platforms were used as the independent variable. As for the dependent variable entered in the model, factors affecting engagement, online activism, offline activism, and activism identification are used to reveal which outcomes contributed significantly. Lastly, the overall mean ($M = 4.97$, $SD = 1.61$) is interpreted as the respondents somewhat agreeing with statements related to activism identification. So, on average, respondents agree to some extent with statements, but there may be variations in the strength of agreement among individual respondents, as indicated by the standard deviation.

Table 6. Multiple Regression Analysis for Four Dependent Variables

Variables		β	SE B	t	p
Factors Affecting Engagement		0.41	0.12	3.46	< 0.00
Online Activism		0.05	0.11	0.43	0.67
Offline Activism		-0.09	0.10	-0.93	0.36
Activism Identification		0.11	0.08	1.31	0.19

Table 6 reveals that factors affecting engagement ($\beta = 0.41$) were a significant predictor of examining whether there is a relationship between social media platforms and the level of engagement in online activism. At the same time, online activism ($\beta = 0.05$) reveals the weak relationship between online activism and engagement in social media platforms. As for offline activism ($\beta = -0.09$), it was revealed that there is a negative relationship between offline activism and engagement in social media platforms. Lastly, activism identification ($\beta = 0.11$) suggests that although it is not statistically significant, there may be some influence of activism identification and engagement in social media platforms.

The p-value and interpretation for the null hypothesis are also shown in the table above. The hypothesis foresees, "There is no significant relationship between the type of social media platform used and the level of engagement in online activism among Far Eastern University students." Given that factors affecting engagement are the significant predictor with a ($\beta = 0.41$) and a p-value of <0.00, lower than the alpha $\alpha = 0.05$. This means we reject the null hypothesis, meaning there is a significant relationship

between the type of social media platform used and the level of engagement in online activism. According to Cortes-Ramos et al. (2021), with the heightened use of technological devices, more young people are using social media platforms to communicate, increase social participation, and freely express themselves. As per the study by Cooper (2023), as social media platforms continue their popularity, the level of engagement in online activism can emerge by using different social media platforms or applications for activists to promote their message and earn support.

CONCLUSION

The study enlightens the complex relationship between social media platforms and activism among 80 Far Eastern University (FEU) students through a quantitative approach using survey questionnaires, depicting the most and least effective social media platforms that can promote social change and explore the motivating factors for student engagement. The results have shown that Instagram emerges as the most utilized social media platform, with an average answer from the respondents to Instagram “agree,” with a mean score of 6.03. While Thread has an average answer of “rarely” with a mean score of 1.67, it offers minimal engagement among the respondents.

FEU students mainly use social media platforms to communicate with friends and family, seek information, and freely express themselves, which fosters an environment conducive to raising awareness and conversing about social issues. While some aspects, such as exercise control, like wanting someone to do something for them and to tell others what to do, garnered neutral responses—next, the contrasting perspective of FEU students about online and offline activism. Regarding online activism, liking, sharing posts, and generating awareness about social-political issues gathered stronger agreement. As for offline activism, I participated in rallies, engaged in person discussion, debated with a friend or relative, and received a neutral response showing reluctance. This contrast suggests that students are more likely to participate in online activism rather than traditional offline activism for its convenience and perceived safety. Motivation for engagement stems from the desire to stay involved with social-political issues, monitor social-political issues, and the importance of being a social-political activist. Furthermore, the study revealed a significant relationship between the type of social media platform used and the level of engagement in online activism. Factors affecting engagement ($\beta = 0.41$) were the significant predictor in predicting the relationship of engagement in online activism.

These results emphasize the transformative role of technology, particularly social media platforms, as tools for change in shaping modern activism. FEU students, like many in their generation, utilize social media platforms not only for their personal use but also as powerful tools for social change and advocacy. This study provides beneficial insights regarding online activism for activists, policymakers, educators, and social media corporations, offering guidance on effective strategies for leveraging social media platforms to foster positive societal change.

As we progress toward the future, we must continue exploring the evolving landscape of social media activism, considering its impact on different communities and social issues. Further research could investigate the distinctions of engagement across different social media platforms and with a different or bigger demographic group, which can provide a more comprehensive understanding of online activism’s potential and limitations. This study contributes to the growing body of literature on social media activism. It emphasizes the significance of using technology to drive social justice and collective efforts in today’s interconnected world. As technology continues to evolve, our understanding of its influence and role in shaping activism and societal transformation power must also evolve.

RECOMMENDATION

For future researchers interested in adopting the study on social media activism among Far Eastern University students, it is suggested that future researchers widen the scope to include a more varied demographic track development. Also, combining the qualitative and quantitative analysis might provide deeper insights into student experiences and motivation. With social media platforms rapidly changing, researchers must stay updated on the latest developments and features that can help them adjust their strategies to get the most effective social change tools. Collaboration between social media platforms and beacons indicates the common ground that could change the world if they work together on campaigns and projects. With institutions like Far Eastern University, there is a need for activities aimed at developing student activists’ capacity in training, workshops, and mentorship

programs, with social media advocacy as the major focus. By implementing these recommendations, future researchers can help advance knowledge and inform constructive societal change through online activism.

For future studies, you may use the questionnaire link provided: (<https://docs.google.com/document/d/e/2PACX-1vSjF-y60cO9y2fwiqZsC6A5PgLtkfex8QrccQ6vY1W4NPPDfZKzL6guEF7r7vR3w/pub>).

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